

D2.2: Shared learning Action Plan

TRANSFORM

Deliverable description

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D2.1. Shared learning Action Plan

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Summary

This document is an action plan, the deliverable 2.2 of the TRANSFORM project, within WP2 Framework definition, oversight and shared learning, resulting from the work carried-out in the first year of the project for the task 2.4 Shared Learning.

The activities organised from M1 to M12 initiated and set the ground for Shared Learning for year 2 and 3 of the project. BE participation, the T2.4 leader, in close collaboration with the two other cluster leaders (FGB in Lombardy and SfC in Catalonia) organised a number of Shared Learning activities in year 1 of the project to build common ground and define a meaningful action plan. The monthly cross-clusters meetings and the three mutual learning sessions (two workshops, in July and October 2020, and one WP2 session during the project meeting in September) enabled the cluster leaders to gain a deep understanding of needs for mutual learning but also for a domain that they decided to develop: capacity building. It also made appear key priorities for the fulfillment of TRANSFORM objectives and cluster goals at regional level.

This action plan sets the basis for a key activity of TRANSFORM, namely to provide a frame for partners to regularly share updates on ongoing activities, pros and cons of the methodological approach adopted, challenges to institutional changes, and impact of concrete changes achieved. An additional important need that has appeared in the three regions involved in the project is to develop assessment tools and indicators to evaluate the impact of the participatory activities organised by each cluster, aiming to have an impact on regional R&I and more particularly Smart Specialisation Strategy - S3. The action plan includes:

- **Monthly cross-cluster leaders meetings** to make sure the two levels of activities in the project (cluster-regional and consortium-EU) communicate and share learnings throughout the project;
- **Mutual learning activities**, four times a year for all TRANSFORM partners to tackle challenges encountered at regional level, the engagement of the quadruple helix, the implementation of cluster-specific methodologies, the development of local evaluation frameworks and indicators and the coordination of tasks from WP2 and WP7. These activities also include the three Mutual Learning Workshops that are foreseen during project meetings.
- **Capacity building opportunities** addressing various topics including RRI and its implementation in regional R&I frameworks, Smart Specialisation Strategies (S3), the three participatory methodologies tested by clusters, the development of local evaluation frameworks and indicators and the sharing of best practices of hands-on experience of RRI.
- The Shared Learning Action Plan will support clusters' actions towards advocating for the integration of participatory methods at a systemic level in regional R&I policies and S3 in particular,

including the testing of local evaluation frameworks and quantitative and qualitative indicators that will support this systemic change.

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1. Introduction

The Shared Learning Action Plan produced by BE participation aims to be used extensively during WP2 activities of the TRANSFORM project by cluster members, while it also establishes strong links with aims and activities of WP7 (Monitoring and Evaluation).

The specific context and peculiarities inherent to the TRANSFORM project and the three R&I regional ecosystems involved are addressed in **section 2**. In this section we also explain why the time necessary to plan mutual learning activities - based on the collection and analysis of needs and expectations of the variety of actors involved in the regional contexts - was longer than originally planned, explaining the delay to submit the deliverable D2.2.

The creation of the Shared Learning Action Plan was based on a process that followed various steps. The first step was the launch of activities at regional level, focused on the co-design of local action plans and the identification of specific geographical, societal, economic and environmental aspects and needs for each cluster. The second step was the organisation of collaborative sessions to compare the specific local needs and come-up with a meaningful plan for the three clusters. The key priority was to make the Shared Learning Action Plan adapted to the overall objectives of TRANSFORM but also to the particular objectives of the participatory activities implemented in R&I regional ecosystems. In this context, in addition to presenting the Shared Learning Action Plan itself, this deliverable D2.2 also includes a chapter providing insights on the activities that led to development of the Plan (**section 3**). Furthermore, **section 4** provides an action plan for shared learning in TRANSFORM but also for capacity building until the end of the project.

The Shared Learning Action Plan is a living document that will evolve over the course of the project to adapt to TRANSFORM needs at different phases of the project lifetime. It provides a common ground for action, explaining how clusters will regularly share updates on ongoing activities, pros and cons of the methodological approach adopted, challenges to institutional changes, and impact of concrete changes achieved.

The shared learning and mutual learning process will be driven by the objective to lead to the collaborative production of one of the project key outcomes: “D2.5 Policy Recommendations to transforming regional R&I systems towards RRI”, aimed at inspiring regional governments and local authorities who would like to replicate TRANSFORM processes and implement RRI components within their R&I policies.

Shared learning between clusters represents a key element for the achievement of the project objectives, which are:

- To work in regional territories at institutional level with the objective to **make their territorial development processes more open, transparent, and addressing societal needs** in Europe. The aim is to work with the networks of stakeholders involved in regional R&I, focusing on local priorities determined by each regions' Smart Specialization Strategies (S3), while considering the political, economic, social, and cultural context in which R&I takes place to have an impact on regional innovation processes.
- **To empower diverse stakeholders** providing them guidelines, indicators, and tools to enable them to implement and/or engage with the development of responsible regional development processes and evaluate their impact.
- To explore concrete working methods of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) applying **three sound methodological approaches** to local R&I projects as well as to regional strategies of science governance: participatory research agenda setting, citizen science and design thinking for social innovation.
- To advance RRI in territories further to those involved in TRANSFORM, through the extensive **promotion and sharing of best practices, learnings, and the diffusion of governance innovations emerged within the clusters of the project.**

The TRANSFORM clusters

Three European regions are involved in TRANSFORM: Lombardy in Italy, Catalonia in Spain and Brussels-Capital in Belgium. In each territory, regional governments join forces with experienced RRI facilitators, innovation enablers and civil society organisations to achieve more responsible approaches to territorial development. TRANSFORM addresses the challenge by designing, testing and diffusing three strong methodological frameworks in the three regions at the forefront of implementation of S3, which provide approaches and application areas of responsible territorial development through new forms of local decision-making.

All three territories are devoted to supporting and increasing co-creation and participatory processes within their R&I ecosystems, while also being currently busy with the renovation of their regional strategic plans for supporting R&I in the coming years, including updating their S3 strategies. Meaningful exchanges of information between the three clusters will allow both building upon existing regional commitments towards transformative opportunities and strengthening the opening effect on organisations involved. The TRANSFORM regional clusters have decided to adopt different methodological approaches for the local implementation of RRI components. Each of these territories is already committed to and supporting these different approaches within their R&I activities aimed at inclusive territorial development.

In the first year of the project, in addition to developing an overall Shared Learning Plan, the three clusters have worked on mutual learning activities at regional level. For the **Lombardy region**, the main activities carried out by the regional partners have been related to Participatory Research Agenda Setting in the design of the PST, citizen engagement in S3 and regional RRI performance experimental evaluation. The main outputs are online mutual learning exercises to identify and map RRI activities of the region, embedment of RRI in objectives of the next S3 plan and design and implementation of a capacity building exercise.

For the **Catalonia region**, the main activities were to define the role of the local Think Tank which was launched in June 2020 to reflect on the potential of RRI and citizen science, and an overview analysis of the R&I Catalan ecosystem.

For the **Brussels-Capital region**, the main activities were to define the role of their local Think Tank to support the cluster's participatory activities and to help with the assessment of R&I activities looking at the impact on the local public good; an overview analysis of Brussels-Capital R&I ecosystem; and a reflection process with the cluster members exploring the broad topic of circular economy, preparing the work of analysis of community needs and challenges to address.

In addition, each cluster has shared updates on the latest developments of their new Smart Specialisation Strategies and regional R&I programmes, as all three regions are in the process of renewing their S3 plans.

2. Specificities of the TRANSFORM Shared Learning Action Plan

This section details:

Specificities and commonalities of each of the three regional clusters

Updated planning of the engagement of Think Tank members and the development of regional evaluation frameworks and indicators

Reflections on the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on shared learning plans

2.1 Clusters' specificities and commonalities

The Shared Learning Action Plan supports the three regional R&I ecosystems involved in the project in reflecting upon their specificities (i.e. different local priorities and methodological approaches) and commonalities (i.e. the renewal of their regional plans for R&I and S3 frameworks, the need for a stronger valorization of RRI and lack of indicators, and the need for capacity building).

To address these specificities and commonalities, the three cluster leaders (FGB, BEpart and SfC) have exchanged closely through collaborative activities before finalising the plan presented here in D2.2. Rather than defining the plan in the first six months of the project as originally planned, BE participation, in agreement with the two other cluster leaders, has decided to carry extensive analysis to capture all particularities and common priorities.

The work carried out in each cluster to define these elements at regional level has been described in the deliverable D2.3 Report on cluster-specific societal, geographical, economic and environmental frameworks. As concluded in this deliverable, each of the three regions involved in TRANSFORM represents a unique ecosystem, characterised by a specific demographic distribution, specific key challenges that each region is focusing on in order to boost its R&I potential, as well as specific geographic conditions that make each cluster unique.

The key element in common between all clusters is their strong commitment towards RRI, which at the level of the regional governments and funding agencies involved translates into specific actions, funding opportunities, platforms and initiatives to favour the implementation of RRI principles. For all three regions involved in the project, TRANSFORM represents a key opportunity to boost their RRI potential even further, and to assess the benefits that emerge in doing so.

The specificities of each regional framework and a deep understanding of how they affect the functioning of regional R&I are the starting point for the Shared Learning Action Plan, supporting key next steps in the project such as the definition of local action plans, which will detail how each region is going to implement actions towards the strengthening of RRI components.

2.2 Engagement of Think Tank members and definition of local evaluation frameworks

The definition of selection criteria to form Think Tanks in the three clusters, the identification of the experts in these groups and their engagement were also activities closely linked to the development of the Shared Learning Action Plan. When launching the participatory process with partners in each region of the project, cluster leaders rapidly identified a key need to develop local evaluation frameworks and indicators to assess the added value of integrating RRI in S3. Besides the methodological approach for the Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E) of the project, set out in Deliverable 7.1, TRANSFORM cluster members have also expressed the need for locally adapted indicators that can contribute to assessing how TRANSFORMative approaches implemented through the project can contribute to locally-defined priorities, such as for example a better understanding of the variety of actors involved in the regional R&I ecosystem, or the contribution of R&I to the local public good and shared priorities identified with societal actors. The identification of this need has had an impact on several activities of WP2, such as the choice of Think Tank members (reflected in D2.1 List of Think Tanks members), as well as the definition of D2.2 the Shared Learning Action Plan. Both deliverables submission have been postponed to ensure meaningful framework definition, oversight and shared learning. The two tasks evolved in parallel and will feed each other, Think Tanks members being involved in some mutual learning activities and capacity building sessions, but also and mostly in the definition of meaningful local indicators.

2.3 Impact of COVID-19 pandemic

TRANSFORM partners had originally planned to organise activities for shared learning in conjunction with the project meetings (face-to-face). As specified in the Description of Action, it was planned that 'Mutual learning workshops (MLW) of at least half-day each will be held at three project meetings

(M15, M22, M29), to favour exchange between partners. Project partners will combine, when possible, mutual learning workshops with key local cluster activities being held within WP3, WP4 and WP5'.

Following the COVID-19 pandemic crisis that unfolded from March 2020 on, BE participation and the other cluster leaders had to adapt to the restrictions imposed by the health crisis and find new formats for the Shared Learning Action Plan. The impossibility to meet in person had an impact at several levels. For example, partners have not been able to meet face to face for a very long time, nor at local level within the three regions, nor at consortium level, since all project meetings have been carried out online. The reorganisation of all project activities has been complex and time-consuming and it has resulted in a delay of the process planned to put in place the shared learning activities. The format of all project activities, including WP2 shared learning actions, had to be redesigned to fit a completely digital format and still meet the expected objectives. Taking into account the current situation, all activities will be organised online until the COVID-19 emergency allows travelling and meeting in person.

Despite this context, BE participation, in collaboration with the two other cluster leaders and WP7 leader, has been committed to task 2.4, a key element of TRANSFORM. Through regular monthly meetings they have shared updates on ongoing activities, pros and cons of the methodological approach adopted, challenges to institutional changes, and plans to exchange on impact of concrete changes achieved.

3. Activities contributing to the definition of the Shared Learning Action Plan

This section provides a description of the reflections and exchanges from the mutual learning and capacity building activities organised as part of WP2 in the TRANSFORM project from M1 to M12. The activities described contributed to elaborate the Shared Learning Action Plan detailed in section 4, through the collection of needs and expectations from the three clusters.

Clusters have worked extensively within their regional context to bring about knowledge and a shared understanding of RRI and S3 from the beginning of the project until now. The content of this regional work has been presented in D2.3. In addition to this, the three clusters together with the other partners have participated in a number of online events and meetings aimed specifically at WP2 tasks:

- Monthly cross-clusters leaders meeting (January to December 2020)
- Shared learning workshop (July 2020)
- Mutual learning session at project meeting (September 2020)
- Map&Reflect workshop (October 2020)

All these activities led to building common ground and achieving a shared understanding of RRI, exploring together how to make it stronger in the regional ecosystems, brainstorming on building meaningful participatory activities while at the same time identifying possible gaps and specific actions aimed at strengthening their current engagement towards RRI. This section details actions aimed at the identification of the common ground and needs in terms of capacity building and mutual learning.

3.1 Monthly cross-clusters leaders meetings

Since the start of the project in January 2020, the three cluster leaders (Fondazione Giannino Bassetti in Lombardy, Science for Change in Catalonia and BE participation in Brussels-Capital), have met online monthly in cross-clusters leaders meetings. When relevant, the University of Bergen, the partner in charge of monitoring and evaluation, and AIEDL, the partner taking care of dissemination and outreach, were also invited to participate. The aim of these monthly meetings has been (and currently is) to:

- share updates about the activities implemented at cluster level,
- exchange on mutual learning needs and actions to implement,

- identify and reflect on commonalities and challenges faced at regional level in the achievement of core objectives of the TRANSFORM project, namely to open up regional R&I activities to co-create more responsible approaches to innovation, and to test and disseminate co-creation methodological frameworks for the implementation within Smart Specialisation Strategies (S3),
- discuss needs in terms of evaluation and dissemination.

Key outcomes feeding into the Shared Learning Action Plan:

The monthly cross-clusters leaders' meetings, along with all the other activities described in this deliverable, enabled partners to foster a strong collaboration between clusters through sharing of reflections, updates on advancements, and finding collaborative ways to address challenges.

The impact of the monthly cross-clusters meetings in terms of planning mutual learning activities has been to confirm and further define the shared understanding of the aim of these activities. Their goal is to trigger exchange between clusters about their regional activities, more particularly, the implementation of the participatory methodologies (participatory research agenda setting in Lombardy, citizen science in Catalonia and design-thinking for social innovation in Brussels-Capital). The objective is to work on the common challenges that clusters are facing and find collaborative ways to address them while also collaborating with the Advisory Board to obtain their support and feedback. A list of key topics and themes that emerged from monthly discussions among clusters, that contributed to the definition of the Shared Learning Action Plan and that will be addressed in its activities, are presented below:

Definition of capacity-building activities

As part of their monthly cross-clusters meetings, a number of key reflections were shared and actions decided:

- **Regional partners involved in each cluster need to be supported and build capacity on RRI and its application in regional R&I.** For example, the Brussels-Capital cluster noticed that the process to reflect on and design the collaborative activities with the members of its cluster needed a longer time dedication than expected. The partners are familiar with the concept, but they need extensive knowledge sharing and more examples of applied RRI before moving on to the action plan creation step.
- The Catalan cluster also identified a need for **knowledge and capacity building around the RRI concept and its application.** In that context, they organised a webinar involving 60 attendees to introduce the topics covered by TRANSFORM to an audience that was quite varied in terms of

knowledge of RRI. The attendees included local government, key public sector agents (waste agencies), universities, research centres including some that have developed citizen science projects, enterprises and innovation laboratories.

The three clusters agreed on the fact that at least part of the capacity building activities in TRANSFORM should aim at proposing inspiring examples of participatory processes, citizen engagement, and other key concepts useful in the project. Targeted actors should be able to relate to these examples, and the local context should be taken into account. Cluster leaders also highlighted the fact that Advisory Board members could contribute to this process by sharing information on some of their projects, experiences and practices. Key action points that have been identified include:

- Strengthening support to R&I actors to implement RRI
- Better understanding of RRI
- Target policy processes and actors to highlight the added value of RRI
- Empowering actors on their role in co-creation, co-design and participatory processes in general

Definition of approaches towards opening-up R&I and S3

Creating best practices through embedding RRI in existing R&I initiatives

During the cross-clusters meetings, cluster leaders shared reflections on the best approach to adopt at local level when moving forward in the implementation phase of the project activities. For example, the Brussels-Capital region cluster considered several options, ranging from building an ad-hoc pilot project that would serve as best practice of RRI implementation for the region, up to focusing instead on implementing RRI components within ongoing R&I projects. Sharing between cluster leaders of such common challenges has been fundamental in the current definition of action plans which are in line with TRANSFORM pillars while also taking into account regional specificities.

Influencing funding of R&I programmes

One of the key aims of TRANSFORM is to ultimately impact the way regions support the achievement of S3 priorities, through the implementation of stronger participatory processes. Cluster leaders have spent time discussing how this could best take shape in their particular regional context. For example, the Lombardy regional cluster strategy is to engage external guests from public administrations who are working on the definition of R&I grants and preparing funding programmes. In addition, the Lombardy regional government involved in the cluster is very interested in the measurement of RRI in S3 plans. In Catalonia, the regional R&I public entity involved in the cluster has been trying to introduce

RRI in S3 for many years. The cluster leader realised that for them, embedding RRI in research projects is already taking place, while they struggle with the implementation of RRI in S3.

Impact assessment

While developing D7.1 on TRANSFORM Monitoring and Evaluation framework, partners from the University of Bergen (WP7 leader) had close exchanges with the partner organisations of the three clusters. A key observation that emerged from these exchanges with local partners has been that the methodology and indicators should be not only widely accepted by the regional stakeholders involved in the project, but also useful to them to advocate for stronger RRI in the future, while contributing to better understanding their ongoing RRI activities.

Measuring RRI performance at regional level, co-creation of indicators

Extensive discussions about the measurement of RRI performance have taken place during these cross-clusters meetings. For example, the Catalan cluster leader reported that the regional government believes that developing indicators is very difficult and raised the question about using qualitative tools to measure the RRI impact instead. According to the Catalan cluster, it is important to pay attention to develop indicators that can be applied to the ecosystem in question, and that can measure the change on policy-making. The indicators should be specific to the participatory activities, developed for a small scale application. The aim is then to scale them up at the R&I ecosystem level and not the other way around, namely developing indicators made to analyse impact at the ecosystem level that are then leveled-down to the TRANSFORM participatory activities. In Lombardy, the cluster is interested to see the impact of RRI (elements, procedures, etc), to be embedded in regional activities to support local R&I, on local R&I advancement. To start this kind of process, the Lombardy cluster would like to measure and analyze its own RRI performance, according to clear and transparent indicators.

The cluster leaders reached the conclusion that different clusters have different approaches for the impact monitoring framework they would like to test. Most importantly, TRANSFORM clusters recognised the common priority to the three regions, namely the need to be able to evaluate the impact of integrating RRI in S3. Regional public institutions in charge of the R&I policies and of formulating R&I programmes and S3 strategies need to have a way to measure the impact of changing the way R&I is done, integrating RRI. A key priority is to convince public administrations to use new indicators to measure R&I performance, indicators that include RRI dimensions. This could also be a good example for other actors like companies or research centres new to RRI towards adopting new approaches. Having a way to valorise RRI impacts is a key priority to convince companies and other stakeholders to adopt these principles. It has been agreed that TRANSFORM should advocate for the (co)-creation of local evaluation frameworks and quantitative and qualitative indicators.

In collaboration with the evaluation WP of the project (WP7), the regional clusters have therefore decided to co-create indicators at local level to measure the impact of the TRANSFORM activities on the R&I policies and ecosystems, in particular with regard to their contribution to the local public good. For this co-creation of indicators, the cluster leaders raised the point that the conversation does not get meaningful results if it remains broad, at a conceptual level. Concrete local cases and running case-based discussions will help create meaningful indicators. The involvement of civil society organisations and citizens will help identify possible missing elements. The participatory process should be based on specific thematic practices and local cases to help citizens feel engaged and see the impact.

TRANSFORM regional Think Tanks

The three clusters exchanged on the role the regional Think Tanks should take and compared the way these groups of experts are planned to be involved.

The Lombardy region cluster will involve the Think Tank to evaluate the impact of RRI on policy-making at the research agenda setting phase. The experts have been selected for their knowledge of RRI and solid experience of the R&I ecosystem of Lombardy. The cluster will have two parallel pathways: to have a small think tank of maximum 20 persons (more involved) and a larger group for capacity building and awareness raising. The network of cluster partners and the context of the Lombardy region influenced the selection of the Think Tank experts. The Catalonia Region cluster has already involved a significant group of experts, representatives from different innovation sectors and different groups of the quadruple helix, engaged in their Think Tank. The objective of the Catalan cluster is to promote networking capabilities amongst these experts, working on capacity building with them so as to integrate the participatory methodologies that can have an impact on the R&I ecosystem that can be evaluated. Their approach is to also define indicators with Think Tank members that can be later embedded in future calls for proposals of the region. For the Brussels-Capital Region cluster, the Think Tank experts are expected to also support the co-creation and the implementation of the evaluation framework at local level.

3.2 Mutual Learning Workshop - July 2020

This mutual learning workshop aimed to share key points of clusters' activities so far, trends emerging in the three regions, like the renovation of their S3 and regional plans for R&I, and an update on the evaluation framework. In addition, the workshop's main objective was to carry out group discussions

on the implementation of RRI in regional R&I to help define the mutual learning activities and capacity building needs. The following paragraphs summarise the outcomes of the group discussions.

First group discussion session

The first discussion focused on both assessing the barriers to implementing RRI and the indicators needed to measure R&I performance. The aim was to collect data to plan the mutual learning activities and capacity building sessions. The group discussion was organised by ‘type of actors’ involved in TRANSFORM clusters: one group was composed of regional governments, while the other group was composed of research partners and public/science engagement partners.

Before launching the discussions, moderators reminded the key dimensions of RRI: Gender, science education, public engagement, ethics, open access, governance.

The first question the two group were asked to answer is:

- 1. ‘In your experience, which barriers do you face in implementing RRI in your R&I (or R&I-related) activities in your region?’*

Regional governments

Main barriers identified and taken into account for the Shared Learning Action Plan include:

- Lack of statistical and execution indicators
- Existing indicators are not suitable as they are focussed on outcomes or on economic criteria (like patent and budget).
- Need for indicators that can measure transformative processes, qualitative criteria and social, environmental challenges at territorial level. The indicators should inform policy. The combination of the indicators should help provide the whole picture.

Research partners and public/science engagement partners

The exchanges about the barriers were gathered in a PADLET board, the outcomes can be seen in the figure below.

- Governance: Current universities' governance is characterized by centralization but a high distribution at the same constitutes a barrier to embrace RRI.
- Public engagement and citizen participation:
 - From the point of view of a university, it is difficult to reorient a project integrating citizen's perception, participation and priorities. The main barrier relies on the way to access citizens. There are no easy channels to make citizens participate. Each research group has to create their own ones.
 - Citizen participation is seen as time consuming with no resources allocation.
 - To enable citizen participation, research language needs to be adapted, which is a difficult task.
 - Lack of shared infrastructure to include citizen participation.

The second question this group discussion was aimed to answer:

2.'If you could suggest three measurements/ indicators of R&I performance in your region, what would those be?'

The measurements and indicators proposed are summarized as follows:

- Number of Open datasets, and number of data reused.
- Involvement of civil society organisations.
- Diversity of stakeholders in a given project (inclusiveness).
- Ranking of options: Ask different stakeholders to rank research options (characterizing research questions and methodology) before and after a research related participatory process.
- Gender balance in research projects and in participatory activities with citizens or other stakeholders.
- Citizen participation in decision making processes.
- Ability to transform science into policies / evidence-based actions.
- Indicators to measure if the research has reached society: Number of open access publications, dissemination materials addressed to the general public, number of interactions in social media, number of participatory events, workshops, etc.
- Co-creation of the research question with key quadruple helix stakeholders.
- Evaluation of the impact of the research project at the local level: What has changed? Has it impacted people's lives? Has it increased the science literacy level of society? What difference for society has it made?

Second group discussion

The second discussion aimed to answer the question:

'What are the biggest challenges you are facing in your cluster activities taking into account both short-term and long-term objectives?'

The challenges faced in cluster activities were shared and gathered in a PADLET board visible in the figure below.

The Padlet board is titled "What are the biggest challenges you are actually facing in your cluster activities?" and includes the instruction "Think both short-term and long-term". It features 15 cards with the following titles and content:

- How to link local-regional indicators, and to make interregional comparisons:** Needed for the mapping.
- Citizen Engagement methodologies:** Citizen engagement needs robust methodologies. Not all the members of the cluster have skills and experience on this.
- The RRI is a not very concrete and edible concept, how do we get it down to earth, to make it practical?:**
- Dialogue:** Dialogue with partners within the cluster - letting them know RRI better than what they think already know it and encourage them. This is not easy because we cannot meet in person yet.
- RRI is not just a nice thing:**
- Timing:** Dealing with agenda setting, actions need to be implemented NOW.
- Innoviris being understaffed at the moment (only 3 persons working out of a team of 6). Reduced time dedication.** They have very lengthy hiring processes (10 to 12 months) so it is quite likely that this situation will last for long.
- How to work with different backgrounds and fields: less/more experts; less/more interested in RRI:** If we want to reach the R&I ecosystem we need to put together many different people.
- To find specific institutional tools where public participation can be introduced and which could be aligned in the different institutions:** Having an impact on the new Regional Plan for Innovation (Brussels) that is currently under development. Innoviris has selected a company called Idea Consult (through public procurement) to run the multi-stakeholder consultation process - they are running out of time, stressed about the current situation, and I struggle to keep them focused on linking with TRANSFORM.
- Defining the work at two different levels:** 1) The pilot / more local & sectorial level 2) The ecosystem level - what is our definition of R&I ecosystem? Shall we include all the territory? Shall we include representatives for all the priorities of the S3? How many 4thelx organizations we need to invite to reach a critical mass for the mapping?
- The scope of the pilots:** In Catalonia we are imagining things far beyond the scope of TRANSFORM, which poses a risk on implementation if we don't get additional funding (which Tatiana is confident that we will get).
- S3 is sooooo complex:** So many actors are involved in and we cannot interact with all of them.
- Connecting with S3:** In Brussels the new Regional Plan for Innovation will inform the new S3 strategy plan, by identifying specific local challenges and seeing how local R&I is addressing them.
- Info on S3:** Quite complex in terms of actions already implemented, people in charge of it, etc.
- Change in policy priorities:** Due to COVID-19, the call for innovative waste collection systems in municipalities, which was the base for our pilot selection in Catalonia, together with all the calls related to S3, have been frozen to invest all funds in health issues - Tatiana does not agree, but this is a decision from higher levels - now all municipalities are complaining, but we don't know what will happen.

The outcomes are summarized here and will be taken into account in the implementation of the Shared Learning Action Plan:

- Geographical scale of action and evaluation: How to link local-regional indicators with other contexts? How to carry-out interregional comparisons?
- Uneven experience and knowledge of actors involved multiplicity of actors:
 - Citizen engagement needs robust methodologies. Not all the members of the cluster have skills and experience for this.
 - How to work with different backgrounds and fields with different levels of expertise and interest in RRI? To reach the R&I ecosystem as much as possible, many different people need to be put together.

- Capacity building for partners within the clusters: increasing their knowledge of RRI and encouraging them, particularly challenging due to the COVID-19 context and the impossibility to meet in person.
- Entry point for public participation in institutions: To find specific institutional tools where public participation can be introduced and which could be aligned in the different institutions
- Having an impact on the new Regional Plan for Innovation that is currently under development.
- Defining the work at two different levels: 1) The local & sectoral level 2) The ecosystem level - what is the shared definition of R&I ecosystem? Shall all the territory be included? Shall all representatives be included for all the priorities of the S3? How many quadruple helix organisations need to be invited to reach a critical mass for the mapping?
- Connection with S3:
 - In Brussels-Capital the new Regional Plan for Innovation will inform the new S3 strategy plan, by identifying specific local challenges and seeing how local R&I is addressing them.
 - S3 is complex, many actors are involved and it is not possible to interact with all of them.
- In Lombardy: A challenge related to timing is the fact that dealing with research agenda setting, actions need to be implemented right now.
- In Catalonia:
 - Change in policy priorities: Due to COVID-19, the call for innovative waste collection systems in municipalities, which was the theme selected for TRANSFORM participatory activities in Catalonia, have been frozen to invest all funds in health issues at the same time as all the calls related to S3.
 - The scope of the participatory activities: In Catalonia the cluster is projecting its activities on the long-term, far beyond the scope of TRANSFORM, which poses a risk from implementation point of view, as additional funding will be needed.

3.3 Mutual learning session at project meeting - September 2020

This mutual learning session was an item on the second project meeting agenda held on 28 and 29 September 2020. It consisted in a participatory activity with all TRANSFORM partners coordinated by BE participation. The main question was:

‘How can capacity building and mutual learning support the concretization of needs and expectations that emerged in the previous session?’

Four categories of needs emerged:

- **Strengthening the support** in research and innovation for implementing more RRI components. Some researchers are aware of RRI but still need support, others are not aware at all of the RRI concept.
- **Better understanding of RRI** in the research and innovation context. Sometimes it is challenging to find the right stakeholders to involve in RRI processes. Once the right people are around the table, the process becomes easier.
- **Policies:** not only RRI should be supported through specific funding, but RRI actions should also be embedded and valorised within overall R&I funding programmes and policy making processes.
- **Indicators** are needed to build stronger arguments around RRI and make the case for a long-term impact of the TRANSFORM actions.

A key question that operates at the intersection of these needs is: *How to disseminate TRANSFORM's work to other actors?*

The discussion emerging from this question mainly concerned the actors involved and the way to engage them.

On citizen engagement, partners highlighted the importance of sharing concrete examples of what a participatory process is. Many citizens and other actors ignore what they are engaging in when signing-up for participatory processes. Stakeholders should understand what their role is in the co-creation/co-design process.

It is important to inform researchers about the policy-making structure of R&I and the focus on S3. The final aim is to support researchers and innovators to be more aligned with societal needs.

During this session, an important role the TRANSFORM project was reinforced: to provide some tools to make the co-creation cycle easier for policymakers and to inform researchers and innovators that there is a possibility to share their ideas, their daily jobs and collaborate with policymakers.

It was also reminded that the TRANSFORM project enables to extend existing networks, with sharing of good practices and information on added values of multi-stakeholder engagement at national and local level beyond the lifetime of the project.

Other key elements emerged throughout discussions:

- It is necessary to dialogue, to find a common ground and to overcome barriers to regularly come-up with solutions like the incentives for researchers.
- In TRANSFORM, the cluster leaders have the role to overcome these barriers and work as facilitators in the triple or quadruple helix.

- For the capacity building to be useful, clusters should be very clear with their action plan, needs and priorities upfront. During the project meetings each cluster could teach each other by sharing concrete actions that each one has carried out in their region. The idea is to go from abstract and global terms like RRI or S3 to concrete participatory activities and experiences.

Conclusions and takeaways from this mutual learning session

Each cluster is building an action plan for participatory activities to create new inspiring examples of quadruple helix collaboration. At the European level, the idea is to share a cross-cluster vision on RRI and create cross-cluster sharing, collaboration on the common topic of TRANSFORM, e.g. how to have more RRI into regional policies and more particularly in S3 plans. The aim is the mutual learning between clusters for this common goal.

TRANSFORM partners have tools to share mutual learning that can address the needs emerged from discussions so far, and a series of actions can be implemented:

- Capacity building and mutual learning
- TRANSFORM can support researchers, staff from public administrations involved in the project (Innoviris, GENCAT and Regione Lombardia)
- WP2 can provide examples, experiences, inspiring practices
- The capacity building should focus on concrete needs, rather than general training
- TRANSFORM can help actors and users to understand that they can have an active role in R&I policy processes

The international partner of the TRANSFORM project, the Museum of Science of Boston, also shared their own experience in this domain within the context of the CC-PES project and explained that this kind of cross-cluster learning has been helpful. CC-PES has also performed similar activities such as the TRANSFORM workshop (and WP2 activities in general). For example, the CC-PES policy partners have discussed together how to develop a common understanding of what their experiences were like.

3.4 Map & Reflect Workshop - October 2020, building common ground

The Map & Reflect workshop was organised as part of the WP2, task 2.3: REFLECT. The aim was to share critical elements identified by each cluster within their SWOT analysis and define collaborative propositions on how to improve the openness and inclusiveness of regional R&I ecosystems. The results of the regional SWOT analysis and the identification of common elements by BE participation,

as task leader, has been presented in D2.3 Report on cluster-specific societal, geographical, economic and environmental frameworks. A summary of this comparison is presented in the figure below as it is also relevant for the Shared Learning Action Plan presented in this deliverable D2.2.

The group discussions that were based on this identified common critical elements led to define a number of actions that are also described in detail in D2.3. As these actions will be taken into account for the Shared Learning Action Plan, figures summarising them are also provided here:

Adressing common SWOT elements –
outcomes of group discussions

Common strenghts (internal) used to reduce risks (extrenal)

COVID-19 crisis

finding actions
that can be
undertaken even
if the lockdown
remains for a
certain period of
time

**Citizen
distrust/fatigue of
citizens**

showing concretely
what the clusters
deliver with their pilot
activities

using participatory
approaches to involve
citizens for recovery
plan and actions

**Lack of RRI
understanding and
measurement**

supporting the
emergence of new
KPIs to support
administrations to
focus RDI policy on
RRI principles with
impact evaluation

Adressing common SWOT elements –
outcomes of group discussions

Addressing comon weaknesses (internal factors)

**discrepancy
between ambition
and reality**

implementing
concrete
actions and not
only spending
time in
discussions

**Citizen
distrust/fatigue of
citizens**

not generating false
expectations

good understanding of R&I
ecosystem in each region

supporting sustainable
capacity building & awareness
raising at cluster individual
level

**Lack of RRI
understanding and
measurement**

improving the
collaboration between
the WP2 and WP7

connecting closely
with the clusters and
their pilot to develop
meaningful KPIs

Adressing common SWOT elements –
outcomes of group discussions

Maximizing opportunities (external factors)

using existing
R&I platforms &
stakeholders
dialogue

more ownership
to other actors
due to activities
organised online,
recordings
available

involving the
private sector as
adopting RRI for
enterprises make
it more align to
the market

3.5 Identification of key action points

Achieving a shared understanding of RRI, exploring together how to make RRI stronger in the regional ecosystem, brainstorming on building meaningful participatory activities led to building a common ground for the TRANSFORM partners.

The TRANSFORM project should provide support to public administrations to **increase the engagement and the collaboration of quadruple helix actors, especially citizens**, in Smart Specialisation Strategy (S3).

BE participation built on previous work done and presented above and proposed concrete ways to address the challenges identified. To do so, the Shared Learning Action Plan proposes activities in four areas: support, understanding and experiencing, evidence to strengthen policies and communication. The activities proposed aim to answer identified challenges:

a. Support

How can TRANSFORM support clusters in strengthening the implementation of an RRI participatory approach beyond the phase of S3 definition and throughout its implementation?’

- Periodic online cross-cluster workshops to share about the implementation of S3 at regional level, and Entrepreneurial Discovery Processes in particular.
- Clusters play a role of “critical thinkers” to each other, pointing to where 4H could be strengthened and sharing experiences.

How can we share information about the way clusters are articulating their S3 implementation and Entrepreneurial Discovery Processes (EDP) and encouraging citizens' engagement through different methodologies?

- Workshops to familiarize partners with the TRANSFORM methodologies (participatory research agenda setting, citizen science and design thinking for social innovation) – with support of AB members
- Cross-cluster workshops to increase awareness of opportunities and benefits of the chosen methodology

b. Understanding

How can clusters build stronger bridges between researchers/innovators and public administrations while at the same time increasing the understanding and motivation to perform RRI?

- Project partners to organise capacity building workshops, within their own institutions, to increase the understanding of RRI and its potential, with the support of cluster leaders.
- Cluster leaders and UiB to support partners by providing concrete examples and inspiring practices of how RRI can contribute to more effective public policies and to R&I contributing more to the local public good.

How can clusters build stronger bridges between researchers/innovators and public administrations while at the same time increasing the understanding and motivation to perform RRI?

- RRI (multi-stakeholder engagement) training for officers working in public administrations supporting R&I.
- RRI (multi-stakeholder engagement) training for R&I project leaders funded by public administrations.

c. Experiencing

How can cluster members get a deeper or “hands-on” understanding of a real 4H process, how it can be done and what it can lead to?

Although this point is particularly complex during COVID-19 crisis, the plan is to organise online sharing, through for example invited guests, i.e. researchers sharing their experience of how they have benefitted from RRI etc.

d. Evidence

How can clusters assess their achievements in terms of making their S3 implementation process more inclusive, democratic, transparent and responsible? How can they showcase the added value of it?

- Local co-creation of impact assessment, success factors, “indicators”. Interesting comparison between clusters.
- Shared reflections on linking stronger RRI to contribution to the “local public good”.
Transformative outcomes

4. Activities for capacity building and mutual learning

The main activity proposed for shared learning is a series of sessions, starting from January 2021 on, that will be dedicated to mutual learning and capacity building. All the sessions will be open to all partners although for each session, the objectives and more specific target actors (researcher, public administration, etc.) will be defined and communicated. Some sessions will involve the whole consortium while others will be more targeted. As long as the global situation impacted by the COVID-19 crisis remains unchanged, the meetings will be organised online. If conditions evolve, BE participation and the two other cluster leaders will discuss how to possibly adapt the format to face-to-face events. The plan and its implementation are coordinated by BE participation with the support of the two other cluster leaders.

There are several types of activities involved in mutual learning and capacity building:

- the **monthly cluster leaders meeting** as a continuation of what has been organised since the beginning of the project
- the **mutual learning sessions** at least 4 times a year, in which all partners are expected to participate. These meetings will be practical, concrete with thematic approaches
- **capacity building** sessions will be organised to answer the needs identified among partners through participatory workshops described in section 3. Partners are strongly invited to attend, unless the capacity building session is specifically dedicated to their area of expertise, in which case they might be invited to contribute as active speakers.
- In addition to the mutual learning activities at EU level, **local activities**, more linked to the regional context will be organised.

4.1. Monthly cluster leaders' meetings

The three cluster leaders will continue to meet monthly in cross-clusters leaders' meetings. Partners from the University of Bergen, in charge of M&E, and AEIDL, the partner taking care of dissemination, will also be invited to attend when relevant. The aim, as described above, will still be to share updates about the activities implemented at cluster level; exchange on mutual learning sessions as they are

organised; evolving needs and actions to implement; identify and reflect on commonalities and differences faced at regional level; discuss needs in terms of evaluation and dissemination.

4.2. Mutual Learning meetings involving all clusters

Mutual learning sessions will start in March 2021 and will happen four times a year until the end of the project. The mutual learning sessions will be a moment to share between partners. The original aim was to organise these sessions in conjunction with the project meetings. They will instead be organised online until the COVID-19 emergency allows travelling and meeting in person.

The three cluster leaders planned the activities collaboratively and decided to find anchoring elements that make the sessions interesting for the partners. They will be related to the collaborative activities that will be implemented at cluster level, like the methodological approaches (research agenda setting, citizen science, design-thinking), the topics (health, circular economy, waste management, etc.) and more specific elements of the clusters' activities.

Cluster leaders and their cluster partners will share their own expertise and experience. The cluster leaders will make sure activities organised in their region including the collaboration with their Think Tank are brought up in these mutual learning sessions. Experts of the Think Tanks will be invited to share their experience and expertise when relevant. At the European level of the project, the Advisory Board members fulfilling a similar role will also be involved when relevant. MoS will also share their collaborative experience in the United States with their practices from the CC-PES project.

The topics of mutual learning sessions will include:

- Finding strategies to address the main challenges encountered at regional level including:
 - the uneven experience and knowledge of RRI of actors involved
 - the geographical scale of actions and impact assessment
 - the entry point for public participation in institutions
 - the impact on the implementation of new Regional Plans for Innovation and S3, to be launched in 2021.
- Disseminating TRANSFORM work to relevant actors of the quadruple helix and tools to engage them.
- The development and implementation of local evaluation frameworks and indicators in Lombardy, Catalonia and Brussels-Capital, with the specificities of the regional context.
- Work on planned tasks of the TRANSFORM project like the MAPPING exercise, an ongoing task of WP2 and all tasks of WP6 and WP7.

4.3. Capacity Building opportunities

For the capacity building activities, the sessions will be organised every two months in 2021. The calendar will be reassessed at the end of the year and adapted if needed for 2022.

The topics chosen and the speakers selected for these sessions - training workshops open to all TRANSFORM partners - are based on the outcomes of the extensive reflection and discussions held during year 1 of the project.

As for the mutual learning sessions, the aim is to have the experience built within clusters brought up at the consortium level but here more particularly to also benefit from the knowledge of external experts.

The aim of the capacity building activities will be to strengthen support to R&I actors to implement RRI; to enable a better understanding of RRI, to target policy processes and actors showing the added value of RRI. It will also aim at empowering actors to play a role in co-creation, codesign and participatory processes in general.

Beyond the objectives of training the relevant actors and providing tools and examples to reinforce their RRI capacities, the aim of these sessions is to advocate for a number of actions that will have an impact on the long-term. These include the integration of participatory methods at a systemic level in regional R&I policies including S3 or the testing of evaluation framework and quantitative and qualitative indicators that will support this systemic change.

The themes addressed will include:

- RRI and its application in regional R&I.
 - How to concretely influence regional policies with collaborative activities?
 - How to approach the RRI concept as an overarching concept including various dimensions?
 - Addressing barriers related to the implementation of RRI and the role each actor of the quadruple helix can play (incentives for researchers, recognition in the scientific curricula, recognition at funding level institutional level).
- The three methodologies tested by clusters: training and best case scenario on research agenda setting; citizen science and design-thinking for social innovation.
- The development of local evaluation framework and indicators to help partners assess the added value of the participatory activities implemented by the three clusters. This theme will be addressed taking into account the different approaches taken by the clusters and the need to assess the impact on the overall R&I ecosystem. It will also take into account the measurements

and indicators proposed during the mutual learning workshop organised in July 2020 for which outcomes are described above. Experts from other EU projects, such as for example MARIE (<https://www.interregeurope.eu/marie/>), will be invited to present their evaluation methodologies.

- Best practices of hands-on experience of RRI in R&I with speakers from the quadruple helix bringing real cases of RRI processes that led to an added value.

In addition to these capacity building activities organised at EU level, the three clusters will continue proposing actions for their partners and local actors involved in their participatory activities, having a key role in R&I in the regions

4.4. Calendar of activities

The following table shows the current planning of Shared Learning actions for 2021, including both mutual learning and capacity building sessions. The calendar might be adapted while the project evolves.

Month	MUTUAL LEARNING SESSIONS	CAPACITY BUILDING SESSIONS
Jan.		Presentation of indicators & evaluation tools developed in the context of the EU project MARIE - MAInstreaming Responsible Innovation in European S3. <u>With the contribution of the AB member: Giulia Bubbolini</u>
Feb.		Collaboration with civil society organisations for citizen engagement. <u>Possibly involving the AB member: Angela Pereira</u> and invited speakers
Mar.	Strategies to address main challenges encountered at regional level - multiplicity of actors, entry point for public participation in institutions, impacting new S3	
April		Implementation of new S3, presentation of new priorities and actions, linked with TRANSFORM participatory activities
May	Sharing on the process of development of indicators and local evaluation framework	
June		Capacity building on participatory methodologies: Participatory Agenda Setting. <u>Possibly involving the AB member: Simon Burall</u>

July	Exchanging on the implementation of participatory methodologies in regional context	
Aug.		
Sept.		Capacity building on participatory methodologies: Citizen Science. <u>Possibly involving the AB member</u> : Louise Francis
Oct.	Disseminating TRANSFORM work to relevant actors of the quadruple helix and tools to engage them	
Nov.		Capacity building on participatory methodologies: Design-Thinking for social innovation. <u>Possibly involving the AB member</u> : Anna Meroni
Dec.		

The following table shows planned activities for Shared Learning in 2022. The calendar might be adapted while the project evolves.

Month	MUTUAL LEARNING SESSIONS	CAPACITY BUILDING SESSIONS
Jan.		A hands-on experience of RRI in R&I with invited speakers from the 4H, to bring real cases of RRI processes that brought to an added value.
Feb.	Mutual Learning meeting - specific focus to be defined	
Mar.		Measuring RRI impacts on regional R&I institutions and policies.
April		Capacity building session 9
May	Mutual Learning meeting - specific focus to be defined	
June		Capacity building session 10
July		
Aug.		

Sept.	Mutual Learning meeting to prepare the final TRANSFORM event	
Oct.		Capacity building session 11
Nov.		Capacity building session 12
Dec.	Mutual Learning session at final TRANSFORM event	

5. Conclusion

Thorough analysis of specificities and commonalities of the three TRANSFORM regions R&I ecosystems, and under the impact of unprecedented and unexpected challenges brought about by the COVID-19 pandemic crisis, TRANSFORM partners have managed to work together on the identification of challenges and interesting opportunities for the Shared Learning Action Plan. These elements impacted the definition of the plan and its timeline and led to an adaptation from the original proposal described in WP2.

Despite the postponed submission of the D2.2 Shared Learning Action Plan, BE participation, in collaboration with the two cluster leaders FGB and SfC, organised various activities at cluster and consortium level for mutual learning. The monthly cross-clusters meetings and the three online mutual learning sessions (July, September and October 2020) constituted the necessary activities to design a meaningful Shared Learning Action Plan adapted to the needs of the regional public administrations involved in the project and the other partners. These exchanges between clusters helped identify priorities for mutual learning, topics for future sessions and highlighted a great need for capacity building at cluster and consortium level. Another key point is the clear need that emerged from consultation with partners in the three regions, namely the development of local indicators anchored in regional contexts.

This document reflects this adaptation process, including the description of mutual learning activities throughout year 1 of the project, and key take-aways that helped define a common ground for mutual learning. The deliverable also integrated capacity building activities in the planning.

Monthly cross-cluster leaders' meetings will continue to be organised once a month to make sure the two levels of activities in the project (cluster-regional and consortium-EU-international) communicate and share learnings throughout the project.

The **mutual learning activities** will be organised four times a year and will involve all TRANSFORM partners. They will tackle challenges encountered at regional level, the dissemination of TRANSFORM work to relevant actors of the quadruple helix, the implementation of local evaluation frameworks and indicators and the coordination of tasks between WP2 and WP7.

The **capacity building opportunities** will start with a calendar of a session every two months in 2021, and their planning will be reassessed at the end of the year to adapt if needed in 2022, based on possible new needs that will be emerging throughout. The themes addressed will include RRI and its application in regional R&I, the three participatory methodologies tested by clusters, the development of local evaluation frameworks and indicators and best practices of hands-on experience of RRI.

All these activities aim to empower actors to play their role in co-creation, co-design and participatory processes in TRANSFORM. Beyond the objectives of supporting the relevant actors and providing tools and examples to reinforce their RRI capacities, the aim of this Shared Learning Action Plan is to advocate for a number of actions that will contribute to the long-term impact of the project. These include the integration of participatory methods at a systemic level in regional R&I policies and S3 implementation, and the testing of local evaluation frameworks and quantitative and qualitative indicators that will support this systemic change

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